

	California	Florida	Massachusetts	Mississippi	New York	Texas	California	Florida	Massachusetts	Mississippi	New York	Texas
COVID Impact Survey												
mask use												
April	91%	78%	NA*	NA*	93%	76%	1.08	0.92	NA*	NA*	1.10	0.90
May	92%	84%	NA*	NA*	95%	90%	1.02	0.93	NA*	NA*	1.05	1.00
June	97%	91%	NA	NA*	98%	90%	1.03	0.97	NA	NA*	1.04	0.96
social distancing												
April	87%	87%	NA	NA	91%	85%	0.99	0.99	NA	NA	1.04	0.97
May	87%	91%	NA	NA	92%	93%	0.96	1.00	NA	NA	1.01	1.02
June	86%	87%	NA	NA	89%	86%	0.99	1.00	NA	NA	1.02	0.99
Delphi COVIDCast (9/8-11/3)												
mask use high	92.2%	88.8%	96.0%	87.2%	94.3%	88.6%	1.01	0.97	1.05	0.96	1.03	0.97
mask use low	90.5%	83.9%	93.0%	79.0%	91.4%	86.4%	1.04	0.96	1.06	0.90	1.05	0.99
YouGov (3/26-4/29)												
mask use	92%	44%	46%	44%	53%	43%	1.11	0.94	0.98	0.94	1.13	0.91
Premise Global Impact Study (3/15-4/10)												
Extremely familiar with social distancing	45.3%	43.4%	48.7%	33.9%	53.1%	48.4%	1.00	0.95	1.07	0.75	1.17	1.06
social dst. strongly agree	31.5%	31.2%	21.5%	30.4%	34.2%	31.4%	1.05	1.04	0.72	1.01	1.14	1.05
social dst. agree	36.7%	37.3%	48.1%	28.6%	38.6%	42.4%	0.95	0.97	1.25	0.74	1.00	1.10
agree: distancing helps	80%	66.7%	100%	NA	100%	40%	1.03	0.86	1.29	NA	1.29	0.52
							1.05	0.95	1.03	0.93	1.07	0.96
Google MAPs data												
Retail and Recreation	-38%	-22%	-38%	-16%	-42%	-19%	1.31	0.75	1.31	0.52	1.45	0.66
Grocery and Pharmacy	-22%	-14%	-24%	-16%	-23%	-13%	1.19	0.76	1.30	0.81	1.24	0.70
Parks	-47%	-25%	-48%	-13%	-52%	-22%	1.36	0.72	1.39	0.38	1.51	0.64
Transit Stations	-56%	-37%	-62%	-3%	-55%	-29%	1.39	0.92	1.54	0.07	1.36	0.72
Workplaces	-42%	-27%	-40%	-19%	-39%	-29%	1.28	0.83	1.22	0.58	1.19	0.89
Residential	up 18%	up 9%	up 18%	up 6%	up 17%	up 10%	-1.38	-0.69	-1.38	-0.46	-1.31	-0.77
							0.99	1.00	0.99	0.88	1.04	1.03
Apple Data (1/13-11/3)												
Driving	-12%	up 2%	-36%	up 60%	-55%	up 3%	1.31	0.80	1.35	0.47	1.35	0.72
Walking	-16%	up 8%	-39%	up 19%	-71%	up 18%	0.32	-0.05	0.95	-1.58	1.45	0.00
Transit	-58%	-32%	-63%	-15%	-68%	-40%	1.19	-0.59	2.89	-1.41	5.26	-1.33
							1.45	0.80	1.58	0.38	1.70	1.00
							99%					
Unacast COVID19 Dashboard												
Overall Grade	C-	F	C-	D-	D+	F	0.9875	0.05333333333	1.806666667	-0.87	2.803333333	-0.08333333333
							C-	F	C-	D-	D+	F
Unacast COVID19 Dashboard												
	-142	1.32	0.82	1.37	0.42	1.37	0.72					
	65.8	1.31	0.33	2.10	0.97	2.99	0.29					

*Not enough state responses for sub-group analysis